

INNOVATIVE DESIGN OF CLASS 10 TEXTBOOK

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ABSTRACT: Teaching is not an easy matter, as it requires hard work and attempt from the educator. To teach students effectively, good textbooks are essential. This article illustrates some innovative design of textbooks, which are suitable for teaching 10th grades at secondary school.

KEY WORDS: innovative, method, textbooks, books, teaching, biology, teaching methodology.

Biology teaching methodology is the science of learning, processes, principles and laws related to the basics of biology. Knowledge of these principles and laws allows the teacher to organize and manage the educational processes related to the school biology course in accordance with the requirements of the time. The biology teaching methodology aims to introduce the content of biology subjects, its teaching forms, methods, and tools in an interdependent manner.

The main task of the biology teaching methodology is to provide students with in-depth knowledge of biological subjects, to develop the content of subjects, teaching forms, tools and methods that help them grow as well-rounded individuals. consists of drawing. Teaching methodology of biology as a science Any science is related to the research activity of a person, it is aimed at gathering knowledge about things and phenomena, and the subject of research is full and comprehensive about the phenomena. Aimed at gaining knowledge. The main function of science is research. The methodology of teaching biology as a science aims to improve the knowledge, education and development of students related to this science in theoretical and practical terms.

The main sign of science is the clarity of the goal, the subject of study, methods and forms of knowledge acquisition. At the same time, the history of the development of science and the discoveries that led to its enrichment are also considered important. Biology teaching methodology is part of pedagogical sciences. For this reason, the goals and tasks before him are derived from general pedagogical goals and tasks. The methodology of teaching biology is aimed at applying the pedagogical principles applicable to all academic subjects

to the biological educational material. At the same time, the biology teaching methodology incorporates natural, scientific, biological, psychological, and pedagogical knowledge. The teaching methodology of biology determines the teaching purpose, content, and principle of selection of biological knowledge.

The tasks of teaching methodology of biology as a science are as follows:

1. Determining the place of educational science in the education and upbringing of students;
2. Develop recommendations for improving school curricula and textbooks and apply them to school practice;
3. Determining the content of academic subjects and the consistency of learning of the subjects in accordance with the age of the students;
4. Developing teaching methods and organizational forms, taking into account the specific aspects of biological subjects;
5. Identification of necessary equipment for use during training. The biology room is a living corner, the organization of the experimental land area, the designation of natural, pictorial, dynamic, audio, video tools.

Biology is an object of teaching methodology and is an educational process related to this subject. The subject of biology teaching methodology is the purpose, content, teaching methods, forms, education and development of students. Scientific and research methods of biology teaching methodology:

1. Observing the work experience of school teachers and identifying the positive and negative aspects of the activity;
2. Analyzing, summarizing, and clarifying unsolved problems of the data collected in this field and putting forward the necessary working hypotheses for their solution;
3. Conducting pedagogical experiments in schools and comparing the data obtained from experimental and control classes in order to determine whether the hypotheses put forward earlier are more realistic;
4. Analyzing, summarizing and summarizing data obtained from observation and pedagogical experiments;
5. Based on the received information, create methodical articles, manuals and review and confirm the developed opinions in public schools.

Until now, as a result of the pedagogical experiments carried out in the methodology of teaching biology, "Development of biological concepts", "System of teaching forms in biology", "Methods of teaching biology", "Development of ecological concepts in biology", "Development of biological concepts" theories such as "material base system", "methodical training system of student

biologists of Pedagogical institutions for school work" were developed and put into practice. Depending on the biology subjects taught in schools, the subjects "Biology teaching methodology" are "General biology teaching methodology", "Botany teaching methodology", "Zoology teaching methodology", "Man and his health". teaching methodology" and finally "teaching methodology of general biology" is divided into special teaching methodology subjects.

The general methodology of teaching biology covers issues such as the purpose, task, content, principles, methods, tools, forms, history and stages of teaching biology in all biological subjects. Private methods focus on the content of one or another academic subject, such as lessons related to the age of students, extracurricular activities, extracurricular activities, excursions, organization of practical and laboratory activities, equipment, etc. The connection of biology teaching methodology with other subjects Biology teaching methodology is closely related to didactics, which is a part of pedagogy.

If didactics studies the laws of acquisition of knowledge, skills and competences by students, and it develops teaching theories and principles for all academic subjects in school, then biology teaching methodology is related to biology. develops theoretical and practical issues related to the content, forms, and methods and tools of teaching and training. Biology teaching methodology is closely related to psychology. Because the teaching of biology is effective only if it is suitable for the age characteristics of the students. For example, because the diet is unstable in teenagers, i.e. students of V-VI grades, the biology teacher uses several methods during the lesson to replace the students' activities, and taking into account the concreteness of their thinking, uses more visual aids. In the upper classes, since the students' attention has stabilized and their abstract thinking has developed, it is enough to conduct the lessons more in the form of lectures and use one or two methods. 9 Biology teaching methodology is inextricably linked with the science of biology. It contains the fundamentals of almost all areas of biological sciences: botany, zoology, human anatomy and physiology, stetology, biochemistry, embryology, systematics, ecology, evolutionary theory, anthropology, molecular biology.

Correct explanation of the external and internal structure of representatives of living nature, the relationship between life activities and the external environment, identification of plants, fungi, animals, microorganisms, preparation of micro- and macropreparations from them, observation on them, conducting experiments, good theory from the teacher requires knowledge and practical training. But the teacher should be well aware that there are important

differences between school biology and biology. If the main purpose of biology is to create new intermediate knowledge by conducting research on living and dead nature, the purpose of school biology is to provide students with biological knowledge according to their age, i.e. biological knowledge consists of giving concepts, laws, theories and explaining it.

In the school biology course, not science, but the basics of science - the basic information necessary for students. At the same time, the school biology course is not a "minor science", but a system of basic concepts of biology that supports the development and education of students. Teaching methodology of biology as a subject of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education biology Teaching methodology of biology as a teaching subject occupies an extremely important place in teacher training. In the process of teaching this academic subject, the necessary professional knowledge, skills and qualifications for teaching biology are formed.

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